

EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING

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Annotation. This article covers the experience and use of the countries of Europe, America and Japan to improve the system of training professional personnel.

Keywords: professional education, training, labor market, foreign experience, educational programs.

It is advisable to use the experience of Europe, America and Japan in improving the system of training Professional personnel.

The European system for training Professional personnel differs in the improvement of the network and the versatility of educational institutions, the priority of Continuing professional Education, a systematic approach to the use of the principle of educational loans. Educational institutions that train professional personnel, taking into account the development of the European economic system, are full-fledged subjects of market relations. In the conditions of the free market, educational institutions are interested in providing educational services in high quality, which determines the activity of such organizations in search of new educational technologies, modernization of educational and laboratory bases, personnel development and effective cooperation with the Real sector.

Qualified working personnel in Germany belong to the category of the most demanding personnel with a wide range of professional qualifications, engineering creativity, design skills and the ability to work on modern robotic equipment. The main principle in the organization of the German system for training Professional personnel is the dualism of the educational process, which consists in the optimal combination and combination of theoretical training in an educational institution and vocational training on the basis of organizations in the Real sector [1]. An important role in the training of professional personnel in Germany is played by competence centers formed at the expense of contributions from Real sector organizations, which have the most modern

training and production equipment and offer high-quality educational programs to interested users. In Germany, the professional personnel training system ensures the formation of entrepreneurial and managerial competencies in graduates, in addition to the main professional competencies, which ensures the high quality of German products, an active creative process in the field of production and the stability of the labor market. Therefore, more than 60% of the country's labor force has a secondary qualification level.

German companies invest heavily in the organization and development of their training centers, many of which train personnel in the interests of the company, which can be equated with individual universities on the scale of these centers.

The American system for training Professional personnel, showing the level of Independent Education, is characterized by the following main priorities: the academic mobility of students, the important role of foreign languages, the introduction and development of international educational courses in the educational process, including online courses, the optimal harmony of the necessary general and professional competencies of graduates and the active use of The American approach implies the functioning of two-year colleges that train personnel of this qualification level. At the same time, the model of training professional personnel adopted in the United States provides for a significant differentiation of vocational education, in which narrow specialized personnel are trained. The system of training professional personnel in the United States is distinguished by the maximum marketing direction, the principle of constant monitoring of the shortage of professional knowledge in students, the predominance of problem-based educational technologies in the educational process, a multi-level system of professional qualifications, the combination of training in a narrow specialty and a multifaceted profession, integration of theoretical [2].

The formation of vocational knowledge in the Japanese system is carried out, first of all, not in the process of obtaining education in an educational institution, but at the place of work. Educational institutions in the country provide a sufficient level of fundamental education for the development of vocational knowledge. Real sector enterprises, ready for the arrival of young workers with insufficient qualifications, successfully carry out vocational training courses and ensure the formation of new employees with significant professional qualifications for the institution itself. Such courses are carried out on the basis of corporate training centers. The Japanese firm occupies the world's leading positions in the organization of internal education. The approach

of Japanese companies to forcibly pass corporate courses not only young specialists who have recently completed their studies, but also experienced employees working in the company is considered interesting to us. The Japanese model for the training of Professional personnel trains highly qualified working personnel with a tendency to a short-term level of adaptation in the workplace and readiness for its systematic distribution.

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